

Effect of Sewing Process and Enzyme Treatment on the Sewing Thread of Denim Garments

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Abstract:

The Denim market has been able to clinch the pinnacle of demand and commendation as the most popular dress material in the past three decades for all ages. From special wear to regular wear, denim has barged into the acceptance of kids, women, and men. But today's fashion era prefers denim jeans based on their attractive shades & styles, designs, and various types of wash appeals, rather than only their robustness. Today's fashion-conscious consumer requires diversified wash-down treatments such as de-sizing, enzymatic washings with or without stones, decolorization, neutralization, brightening, and finishing as per the market and trend requirements. Being unaware of the impact of all the down treatments on denim, consumer acceptance is based only on the aesthetically pleasing outlook of the denim. Thus, this research paper deals with in-depth insight into the effect of sewing and enzyme treatments on the sewing threads present as an integral part of denim wear for the evaluation of the residual properties with the use of lockstitch and chain stitches. The work has been able to elucidate that chain stitches and acid enzymes are detrimental to the tensile properties of the unraveled sewing threads.

Keywords: Acid enzymes, Chain stitch, Enzyme treatment, Fashion-conscious consumer, Wash-down treatments.

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1. Introduction

The invention of denim in the late 1800^s by Levi Strauss for miners revolutionized the apparel and fashion industry in a variety of forms and style lines [1]. Jeans is a more popular name for denim pants that has evolved into a product that caters to almost every age. The denim industry is growing rapidly every year [2]. Denim is flourishing due to innovative finishes, patterns, and easy care [3]. The denim production capacity is spread over the world, the largest producer being Asia when striping down to the country level, the USA is the biggest single supplier, followed by Indonesia and India occupies 5th place [4]. Most jeans are denim based made from 100% cotton or a blend of 50% cotton and 50% polyester [5].

Usually, denim fabric is used for lower garments, and the wash-down effect is applied in a usually haphazard manner. In making patterning effects on denim, the existing methods are often detrimental to the fiber and are not cost-effective [6]. But today's fashion consumers prefer denim due to the attractive shades, designs, styles, and various types of wash appeals, rather than for its robustness. Denim garments in the past were worn in a raw, rigid, and starch-finished form. But today's fashion requires various types of value-added treatments such as de-sizing, enzymatic washing (with or without stones), decolonization, neutralization, brightening, and finishing [7].

Normally, denim washing is carried out in sewn form of denim garments. The denim garments are subjected to different washing techniques such as rinse wash, bleach, enzyme wash, acid wash, stonewash, sand wash, over-dyed/ tinted look, whiskering, damaged and used look [8]. In denim washing, enzymes play an important role in getting a clean, smooth, fuzz-free fabric surface with reduced tendency of pill formation and improved fabric handle [9]. The quality of denim apparel depends mainly upon the fabric quality, sewing thread type and selection of seams play a major role in garment durability, especially for fashionable denim garments, even

though their contribution may not be reflected in terms of cost and quantity [10]. Seam strength is dependent on the sewing thread strength; a reduction in thread strength during sewing will lead to lower seam strength than expected [11]. Therefore, in order to minimize the sewing thread strength reduction, it is important to understand the contribution of different machine elements or operations during sewing.

Studies on the strength reduction of sewing threads have been an important aspect of assessing their performance during high-speed sewing. The effects of the thread properties, machine parameters, and the number of fabric plies have been investigated. It has been postulated that the reduction in fiber strength and the damage inflicted on fibers during high-speed sewing in an industrial lockstitch sewing machine [12]. Synthetic fibers are being increasingly used to manufacture sewing threads to meet the diverse demands of the sewing process and those of the various end-uses to which the threads are put. Any new developments and modification in synthetic fibers, to achieve better sewing and seam performance requires extensive knowledge of the changes in the mechanical and other properties of the fibers caused by the various stresses imposed on them during high-speed sewing [13].

The sewing thread is subjected to impact, tensile, bending, compressive, shear, and surface stresses during stitch formation. Most of these stresses are cyclic in nature and therefore expected to fatigue the thread and hence the constituent fibers [14]. This may cause some critical flaws and damage to the fibers, which would ultimately affect the subsequent seam performance of the sewing thread. Further, this may also generate a potential weak spot in the thread to result in its breakage at high sewing speeds [15, 16].

The stresses created within the sewing thread harm the processing and functional characteristics of the thread. In an early research work, it was reported that there is up to 60 percent reduction in sewing thread strength after sewing and various reasons are responsible for the reduction including the structural damage, along with dynamic and thermal loading [17]. The change (%) in tensile properties at different stages is calculated according to Equation 1[18].

$$\% \text{ Change in tensile properties} = \frac{T_{\text{Thread after sewing}} - T_{\text{Parent thread}}}{T_{\text{Parent thread}}} \quad \text{-----} \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

(Where, T – Tensile strength of sewing threads)

In addition to the thread strength, the strength of the fabric is an important property that decides and influences the performance of the fabric. Enzymatic treatment of fabrics such as denim is known as one of the finishing treatments with many uses because it creates a special appearance and updates apparel. It is estimated that 80% of denim washing is carried out by cellulase enzyme [19]. Cellulases are added to desized denim fabric in a washing machine, and the combination of enzyme action and fabric friction, as well as mechanical abrasion, produces desired fading and softening effect of the garment [20]. When the fabric is washed and treated with enzymes (neutral and acid), the surface fibers are aggressively removed from the fabric surface [21]. The denim fabric is more damaged by the acid enzyme washing than the neutral enzyme washing [22]. It has been observed that not much work has been conducted on the effect of enzyme-based denim washing on the sewing threads used in denim garments.

This research work aims the study the effect of sewing thread fineness, stitch type, and enzyme type on the mechanical properties of sewing threads unraveled from denim fabrics. The mechanical properties (breaking load, initial modulus, and breaking energy) of the sewing threads unraveled from the seams of denim fabrics are compared with the parent sewing thread properties. Along with it, the effect of enzyme treatment on the sewing thread during the wash-down treatments of denim is also studied.

Therefore, the main objectives of this research work was to study the changes in the tensile properties of unravelled sewing threads of Lapped seams of classical denim jeans prepared with the use of Lockstitches and Chain stitches configurations post sewing processes and also, after the enzyme wash-down treatments in acid and neutral conditions. This was carried out to adjudge the combined impact of both the industrial processes on the severance of sewing threads.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Commercially viable PC core spun sewing threads were sourced from Vardhman Yarns & Threads Ltd., Hoshiarpur, Punjab (India) with three different ticket numbers to be compatible with the chosen denim fabric. The physical and structural details of the sewing threads are reported in Table 1. The 100% twill woven cotton denim fabric with 10.50 oz/yd² (GSM), fabric set of 72 EPI & 40 PPI, and Linear density of warp and weft 7.5 Ne & 9 Ne was sourced for the work. The lapped seamed denim was prepared with lockstitch configurations (LS) on JUKI-DDL-8300N (31234) SNLS machine and Chainstitch configurations (CS) on Feed off the arm (MS-191) as per [ASTM D1683/D1683M-22](#). The machine speed was set at consistent 1500 SPM. To maintain the constant machine speed, a DC shunt motor with an AC to DC conversion Panel was used on both (Lock Stitch and Feed of the arm) sewing machines. The tachometer was also used for the measurement of the speed of the main shaft at every change of machine speed. The DC motor with 220 armature voltage, 2.4 A, 0.37 KW, and 3000 rpm was used as shown in **Fig 1**. The stitch density was kept at 8 SPI and Groz-Beckert (UY 128 GAS) sewing needles with needle numbers 21 & 22 were selected. Cellulase enzyme was chosen in both acid and neutral conditions according to the aesthetic look of the final effect required on denim. The active enzyme specifications are listed in Table 2 [23].

R & B Thickness Tester, Innolab Tensile Tester, Instron tensile tester 4411, Twist Tester, CTT (Constant Tension Transport) Lawson Hemphill tester, CSI abrasion tester and Optical microscope were used for the property evaluation of the sewing threads and fabric.

Table 1 - Properties of sewing threads

Sewing thread type	Code	Thread linear density (tex)	Number of Ply	Twist per inch (TPI)	Tenacity (g/tex)	Modulus (gm/tex)	Breaking Energy (J)	Friction coefficient against Metal Surface	Yarn to Yarn Abrasion, (Cycles to break)	Shrinkage (%)
P-C Corespun	PC90	90	2	14.37	34.34	211.8	1.13	0.08	1890	0.6
P-C Corespun	PC105	105	3	11.78	43.39	217.4	3.48	0.12	2340	0.8
P-C Corespun	PC120	120	3	11.52	47.14	251	4.56	0.17	1962	0.46

Figure 1 - a. D.C. Motor with conversion panel, b. Arrangement of DC shunt motor for lock stitch and feed-off the arm sewing machines.

Table 2 - Enzyme specifications

Specification	Acid cellulose enzyme	Neutral cellulose enzyme
Declared Activity	1500 EGU/gm	2450 ECU/gm

Physical form	Liquid	Liquid
pH at 40-55°C	4 - 5.5	6-8

2.2 Seam Sample Preparation

The modified JUKI-DDL-8300 N (31234) SNLS (stitch class 301) and Feed-off-the-arm DNCS MS-191 (stitch class 401) were used to produce the seams at the stipulated sewing conditions (reported in section 2.1). The fabric samples were cut to convenient sizes of 24×2.5 inches and weft-way seams (Lapped seams) were produced. Identical settings of foot pressure and needle thread tension were maintained at the same level for all the desired seam samples produced. The same combinations of needle and bobbin/looper threads were used for the sampling.

2.3 Enzyme treatment of denim

The denim fabrics were seamed as discussed in section 2.2 and exactly half the number of samples were taken out for the enzymatic treatment using cellulase enzyme (in both acidic and neutral conditions) as per enzyme specification (Table 2).

2.4 Seam unraveling

Stitched samples were unraveled with caution for the needle thread which was further tested for the tensile properties in a similar way as the parent threads. The unraveled needle threads were taken out immediately after the sewing process (S1) and from the enzymatic treated seams of denims (S2), from both the stitch structures. Impact of sewing process and enzyme action on the overall change in the tensile properties was observed from the unraveled sewing threads. Thus, two sets of data were investigated- % change in tensile properties after sewing process alone (S1) & % change in tensile properties after sewing process followed by enzyme treatment (S2).

2.5 Sewing thread and fabric evaluation

The denim fabric was evaluated for Fabric thickness (ASTM D- 1777), Fabric weight (ASTM D-3776) and Fabric strength (ASTM D-5035). The parent sewing threads and unravelled sewing threads were tested for Tenacity (ASTM D-2256), Elongation (ASTM D-2256), Frictional properties (ASTM D-3108), TPI- (ASTM D-1422), Initial modulus (ASTM D-2256), Breaking energy (ASTM D-2256), Abrasion resistance (ASTM D-661), Shrinkage (ASTM D-204) and Optical Microscopy. Sewing thread shrinkage was calculated according to boiling water shrinkage method (ASTM D-204). In this method, the specimen was wrapped in cheese–cloth. The wrapped specimen was subjected to immersion in boiling water and allowed to boil for 30 ± 2 mins, cheese cloth along with the specimen was later removed from the bath. The excess water was squeezed out from the cheese cloth and the specimen was, then removed from the cheese cloth & dried in drying oven at 65°C for 1 hour. The loop length was measured. The shrinkage of each test sample was calculated using the Equation 2:

$$\text{Shrinkage \%} = \frac{L_1 - L_2}{L_1} \times 100 \quad \text{----- (Equation 2)}$$

(Where, L_1 = Original length of the loop and L_2 = Length of loop after exposure).

Figure 2 - Optical Microscope with micro- measure software

For checking the microscopic views of sewing threads, optical microscopic method was used. A microscope was used based on micro- measure software having 400% magnification. The thread was illuminated from below and analyzed with a CCD camera positioned above. The results presented below are invaluable for differentiating structural characteristics from the topical or reflective qualities of the threads (set up depicted pictorially in Fig 2).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Effect of sewing process on tensile properties of unraveled sewing threads

The impact of sewing process on the performance of PC core spun sewing threads was analyzed and reported in Table 3.

a. Effect on tenacity of sewing threads- The tenacity of chain stitch unraveled thread is even lesser than the residual tenacity of the lockstitch unraveled needle threads. It is due to the reason that the needle threads in the chain stitch must travel the full fabric thickness and moreover, lapped seams are produced with the fabric folding, thereby, multiple fabric layers are encountered by the needle threads during each cycle of stitch formation. The coarser sewing threads show the higher % reduction of tenacity in comparison to finer needle threads. The higher reduction is analyzed after sewing process because surface fibres of thread are pulled out due to abrasion with the needle and fabric assembly. The lockstitch unraveled needle threads must reach up to the fabric bed that lies in the middle of the seam composition thickness. This shows lesser strength loss as compared to the chain stitches. But the tension fluctuations in the interlacing processes for lockstitches might have compensated for energy losses due to the combined effect of interloping and interlacing stitch formation processes in chain stitches.

b. Effect on initial modulus of sewing threads- An increasing trend of loss in modulus was observed for the increasing Tex number from 90 to 120. The main reason can be attributed to the increased abrasive damage that causes displacement of plies, loosening of structure and also, the non-contribution of the higher number of surface fibers in thread tension leading to higher loss in initial modulus for coarser needle threads.

c. Effect on breaking energy of sewing threads- The “energy to break” is a parameter directly related to the thread tenacity. As the needle thread Tex increased, the energy to break point also increased for the parent threads. The needle threads unraveled from the chain stitch configurations show the similar trends as for parent tenacity of threads. The greater loss in energy to break for needle threads of chain stitch owe to the fact that greater fabric thickness along with four fabric layers that the needle threads have to pierce to make its way into the seam configuration. The microscopic view of the threads (shown in Fig. 3-4) to elaborate the effect of abrasion effect of fabric on threads during Interlacement & Interloping processes. It can be observed that in parent thread, fibres on the surface were very less. The number of fibres pull out due to abrasion was found to be more on the surface of thread unraveled from chain stitched denim fabric as compared to the surface of threads unraveled from lock stitched denim. These more surface fibres cause more deterioration in mechanical properties of sewing thread during chain stitch process to prepare denims.

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Table 3 - % Change in the tensile properties of sewing threads

Sewing Threads	90 Tex		105 Tex		120 Tex	
	Lock stitch	Chain stitch	Lock stitch	Chain stitch	Lock stitch	Chain stitch
Property						
Tenacity (gm/tex)	32.8	29.9	38.8	34.0	42.0	40.3
% Change	(-4.4)	(-12.8)	(-10.6)	(-21.7)	(-10.8)	(-14.4)

Initial modulus (gm/tex)	209.5	208.1	214.1	212	221.2	207
% Change	(-1.09)	(-1.8)	(-1.52)	(-2.5)	(-11.87)	(-17.5)
Breaking energy(J)	1.08	1.02	2.82	2.64	3.79	3.56
% Change	(-4.4)	(-9.73)	(-18.96)	(-24.13)	(-16.88)	(-21.92)

Figure 3 - Microscopic analysis of threads with the impact of sewing process a. Parent b. Lockstitch unraveled c. Chain-stitch unraveled

Figure 4 - Effect of sewing process on tensile properties of core spun threads a. % Change in modulus b. % Change in Tenacity c. % Change in breaking energy

3.2 Effect of enzyme wash down treatment on unraveled sewing threads for Neutral and Acid cellulase enzyme

The effect of the enzyme treatment on the unraveled sewing threads is tabulated in Table 4 & Fig. 5-6. The trend of the effected properties has been elaborated as under.

Effect on tenacity of threads- Acid enzyme is showing a major loss for both the stitch types for all the Tex numbers of sewing threads in comparison to the Neutral enzymes. Also, acid enzymes with chain stitches show maximum tensile strength loss for all sewing threads. This is due to the reason that acid cellulase works in the pH 4.5-5.5 and are much more aggressive on fibres than the neutral cellulase enzyme that works best in the pH 6-8. This is true even for short process times used for both the enzymes.

Effect on initial modulus of threads- The modulus for lockstitch unraveled threads treated with neutral cellulase enzyme is exhibiting an increasing trend for 90, 105 and 120 Tex threads; On the other hand, the acid cellulase is showing a detrimental effect on all the thread types both for the lock stitch and chain stitch configurations, except for 120 Tex thread in which the modulus is showing an increasing trend.

Effect on breaking energy of threads- It is showing an increasing trend in a similar manner as for thread tenacity. The breaking energy for unraveled thread is showing the maximum negative change for the sewing threads used for making chain stitches treated with acid cellulase enzyme, i.e., the combination of chain stitches and acid cellulase enzyme is the most detrimental to the breaking energy loss.

Table 4 - Effect of enzyme treatment on sewing thread properties

Sewing thread type Property	PC Sewing thread											
	90 Tex				105 Tex				120 Tex			
	Neutral cellulase enzyme		Acid cellulase enzyme		Neutral cellulase enzyme		Acid cellulase enzyme		Neutral cellulase enzyme		Acid cellulase enzyme	
	L.S.	C.S.	L.S.	C.S.	L.S.	C.S.	L.S.	C.S.	L.S.	C.S.	L.S.	C.S.
% change in Tenacity	-2.0	-3.5	-3.23	-4.1	-2.3	-2.9	-3.6	-4.92	-1.7	-2.1	-2.36	-2.79
% change in Modulus	+0.62	+1.62	-0.46	-1.12	+0.42	+0.81	-1.0	-1.37	+0.65	+3.99	+0.05	+3.59
% change in Breaking energy	-1.8	-5.3	-0.88	-6.04	-0.9	-4.34	-3.16	-11.88	-0.22	-4.61	-2.86	-7.46

Figure 5 - Effect of enzymatic treatment process on tensile properties of core spun threads a. % Change in modulus b. % Change in Tenacity c. % Change in breaking energy

Figure 6 - Microscopic views of sewing threads after Neutral and Acid cellulase enzymatic treatment a. Parent Thread b. Lock stitch- Neutral enzyme c. Chain stitch-Neutral enzyme d. Lock stitch- Acid enzyme e. Chain stitch- Acid enzyme

4. Conclusions

Chain stitch configurations had shown greater tenacity loss in comparison to lock stitches. The reason for this can be adjudged as the chain stitch structure is based upon the two processes of interlacing and interloping that resulted in more bending regions in the unraveled sewing threads, which behaved as the weaker sections during tensile load bearing. Acid enzymes have a more pronounced effect on the tensile properties of sewing threads when compared with the effect of neutral enzymes on the same sewing threads. This is due to the accentuated aggressive action of the acid enzyme in a shorter span of treatments time than the neutral enzyme. In addition to it, 105 Tex sewing threads are showing more change in the tensile properties than 90 and 120 Tex.

References:

- [1] NEMAILAL, Tarafder. Denim fabric – An overview. *Man-made Textile in India*, 2008, 387-395
- [2] PETER, Obrist. Weaving preparation of denim. *Journal of Textile Association*, 1998, 58, 5
- [3] PATIL, M. Processing of denim. *Indian Textile Journal*, 1981, 91, 105
- [4] KAN, C. W. Recent development in denim processing technologies. *Colourage*, 2013, 42-43
- [5] ADIVAREKAR, R. V, PAUL, R. and PARDESHI, P. D. Denim: Today and tomorrow. *Journal of Textile Association*, 2001, 63 (4), 139
- [6] BARTON, Judi. Denim's empire continuous to expand. *International Dyer*, 192, 10, 21-24
- [7] REKHA, R. and PURNIMA, D. Machineries for garment and denim processing. *Man Made Textile in India*, 2008, 51 (1), 16-18
- [8] SWICE, Good. J. T., TYNDALL, R. M. and THORNE, J. M. Denim garment processing. *AATCC garment wet processing*, 1994, 6-44
- [9] PAUL, R., PARDESHI, P. D. and MANJREKAR, S. G. Denim weaving & dyeing machinery: An overview. *Journal of Textile Association*, 2001, 62 (3), 115
- [10] RAMACHANDRAN, T. and RAMESH, B. V. Analysis of performance of seams and sewing threads in woven fabric. *The Textile Magazine*, 2007, 49 (2), 34-42
- [11] CARR, H. and LANTHAM, B. *The Technology Analysis*, Textile Book Publishers Inc. New York, 1961, 65
- [12] RAMACHANDRAN, T. and RAMESH, Babu V. Analysis of performance of seams and sewing threads in woven fabric. *The Textile Magazine*, 2007, 34-42
- [13] SALHOTRA, K. R., HARI, P. K. and SUNDERSAN, G. Strength reduction in & damage to fibres during high-speed sewing in an industrial lock stitch: Part II. *International Journal of clothing science and technology*, 1998, 10(1), 64-79
- [14] KAUR, R. Seam strength prediction for work wear fabric: M.Tech Thesis, National Institute of Technology, Jalandhar, India, 2007
- [15] FERREIRA, F. B. N., HARLOCK, S. C. and GROSBERG, P. A study of thread tension on lockstitch machine: Part I. *International Journal of clothing science and technology*, 1994, 6(1), 14-19
- [16] FERREIRA, F. B. N., HARLOCK, S. C. and GROSBERG, P. A study of thread tension on lockstitch machine: Part II. *International Journal of clothing science and technology*, 1994, 6(5), 26-29
- [17] MAZARI, A. and HAVELKA, Antonin. Tensile properties of sewing thread and sewing needle temperature at different speed of sewing machine. *Advance Material Research*, 2013, 62(7), 456-460
- [18] MAZARI, A. and HAVELKA, Antonin. Influence of needle heat during sewing process on tensile properties of sewing thread. *Tekstilec*, 2013, 56(4), 345-352
- [19] DURAN, N. and MERCELA, D. Enzyme application in the textile industry. *Colourage*, 2000, 30(1), 41-44
- [20] BUCHERT, J. and HEIKINHEIMO, L. Treating denim fabrics with *tricolor* reesei cellulases. *Textile Research Journal*, 2000, 70(11), 969-973
- [21] FAOUZI, K., SOUFIEN, D. S. and MSAHLI, F.S. The influence of industrial finishing treatments and their succession on the mechanical properties of denim garment. *Autex Research Journal*, 2009, 9(3), 94-100
- [22] MONTAZER, M. and SADEGHINAM, M. A. Influence of different enzymatic treatment on denim garment. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 2009, 160 (7), 2114-2128
- [23] TRIVEDI, V., SINGH, G.P. and KHANNA, S. Effect of Sewing Process on Tensile Properties of Sewing Threads in Denim Garment. *JTA*, 2018, 11, 260-265
- [24] *Apparel Manufacturing Technology* by T. KARTHIK, P. GANESAN AND D. GOPALAKRISHNAN, CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, 2017
- [25] *Garment Manufacturing Technology*, by RAJKISHORE NAYAK and RAJIV PADHYE, March 2019, Publisher: Elsevier
- [26] CARR and LATHAM's *Technology of clothing Manufacturer* revised by DAVID J. TYLER, 4th edition, (June 23, 2008), Publisher: Wiley-Blackwell